

The Plight of the Modern Woman in the Family in ‘To Room Nineteen’

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Abstract:

Family is the oldest institution of human society. It defines the roles and responsibilities of its individual members as per their sex and age from the perspective of its culture. Family is the ultimate source of safety, comfort, happiness and dependence for its members. In the patriarchal societies the roles and responsibilities are determined from the perspectives of man, the master of family. Doris Lessing’s ‘To Room Nineteen’ is a powerful critique of modern middle-class family. The story vividly delineates the effect of family system on modern women. It is the story of Susan Rawlings who suffocates psychologically, loses her individual identity and alienated emotionally as she is confined within the traditional domestic roles. She struggles to attain her individual identity and autonomy in the traditional societal ideals of domestic fulfillment. The present paper is an attempt to study the plight of the modern woman in plight of the modern woman in family.

Keywords: *Modern Woman, Family, Society, Autonomy, Identity.*

Rationale:

During the 20th Century women had the access to education, the weapon of inner as well as outer reformation. It is education that enabled women to attain financial, psychological, social, political, professional autonomy which evolved women into modernity. However, when it comes to family, which operates on the principle of interdependence of its members, this modern woman is torn between her familial responsibilities and her autonomy. Being a part of family, a woman has to play the roles assigned to her ideologically and culturally and being educated she aspires to be autonomous and construct her own identity beyond the so-called identity of motherhood and wifehood. Such dilemmatic situations lead to her plight. Doris Lessing has very effectively depicted the plight of

the modern woman in her seminal short story, ‘To Room Nineteen.’

Objectives of the Study:

1. To consider the life of the modern educated employed woman before her marriage.
2. To consider the life of the modern educated employed woman after her marriage.
3. To consider the plight of the modern educated intelligent woman as depicted in Doris Lessing’s ‘To Room Nineteen.’

Hypothesis:

Traditionally women are assigned the role of looking after the home, giving birth to children and taking care of them. They have to perform the duties inside the home. During the 20th century under the influence of education, life of women underwent a drastic change. Along with the

family life, women become aware of their personal and professional achievements. The responsibilities of the family hinder their professional development. They are caught in a plight to choose either the family or professional growth. Doris Lessing's short story, 'To Room Nineteen' depicts the plight of a modern educated woman.

Methodology:

The researcher has used qualitative research which involves several methods out of which natural observation method has been used here. The method offers the space to present the observations about the topics to be researched. The present paper is composed of the observations of the researcher about the status of modern women in family with reference Doris Lessing's short story, 'To Room Nineteen.'

Explanation:

Education leads to transition. It creates conscientization among people. During the 20th century education changed the life of women drastically. It made them aware of their own personal problems. The educated intelligent women have to look after their personal inner-outer growth and family. This has put them in the plight and Doris Lessing's celebrated short story, 'To Room Nineteen' honestly depicts this plight of the modern women.

Doris Lessing was a prominent writer of the 20th century. In her works she has explored powerfully politics, psychology, gender, and society. Identity, feminism, racial injustice, and the individual's struggle within the oppressive social system are the frequent themes of her literary works. She boldly criticizes societal norms. Her writing offers deep understanding of human consciousness. She was honoured with the Nobel Prize in Literature in 2007.

'To Room Nineteen' was published in 1958. It shows the socio-cultural ideologies imposed on women in the mid-20th century. Susan Rawlings is the central character. Apparently, she is a satisfied wife and mother, but slowly she feels disappointed with her role in her family. Though she has a perfect family, Susan has to face deep inner conflict which shows the veiled struggles of modern women confined by ideologies of traditional family roles. The story reveals the contradiction between societal ideals of marriage and the psychological reality of women's lives. Women, especially in Western societies, questioned traditional domestic roles as they got education, still they were confined within socially constructed expectations of marriage, motherhood and domesticity. Susan Rawlings represents the educated, rational and seemingly liberated women of the mid-20th century. The present paper is a humble attempt to analyze the status of women in the context of the illusion of the ideal family, the restrictions of gender roles, loss of identity, psychological implications of suppression.

The story opens with the reference to the end of the story: 'This is the story I suppose about a failure in intelligence: the Rawlings marriage was grounded in intelligence'¹. It is further pointed out that the Rawlings' decision of marriage had mature background:

They were older when they married than most of their married friends: in their well-seasoned late twenties. Both had a number of affairs, sweet rather than bitter, and when they fell in love-for they did fall in love-had known each other for some time. They joked that they had saved each other "for the real thing."¹ That they had waited so long (but not too long) for this real thing was to them a proof of their sensible discrimination. A good many of their friends had married young, and now

(they felt) probably regretted lost opportunities; while others, still unmarried, seemed to them arid, self-doubting, and likely to make desperate or romantic marriages.

Not only they, but others, felt they were well-matched: their friends' delight was an additional proof of their happiness. They had played the same roles, male and female, in this group or set, if such a wide, loosely connected, constantly changing constellation of people could be called a set. They had both become, by virtue of their moderation, their humour, and their abstinence from painful experience, people to whom others came for advice. They could be, and were, relied on. It was one of those cases of a man and a woman linking themselves whom no one else had ever thought of linking, probably because of their similarities. But then everyone exclaimed: Of course! How right! How was it we never thought of it before!

And so they married amid general rejoicing, and because of their foresight and their sense for what was probable, nothing was a surprise to them.¹

In this way, Susan and Matthew make a family. Susan resigns her job in an advertising firm. Both of them leave their flats and live together in 'their charming flat for two years, giving parties and going to them, being a popular young married couple.' In the course of time Susan gives birth to four children- son, daughter and twin (son and daughter). She resigns her job in the advertising firm. The family has Matthew's well-paid job for the sake of 'Susan, children, house, and garden' and 'Susan's practical intelligence for the sake of Matthew, the children, the house and the garden-which unit would have collapsed in a week without her.' They exemplify

a perfect modern couple with rationality, mutual respect, and shared values. But Susan experiences a sense of dissatisfaction that commonly found among housewives despite the availability of material comfort. Susan loses her individuality and is engaged in daily routine lacking intellectual stimulation and her desires are suppressed in favour of the stability of her family.

In her personal family life Doris Lessing had questioned these ideologies of family system. She married twice and divorced both her husbands. Later on, she observed that she saw no choice then, "For a long time I felt I had done a very brave thing. There is nothing more boring for an intelligent woman than to spend endless amounts of time with small children. I felt I wasn't the best person to bring them up. I would have ended up an alcoholic or a frustrated intellectual like my mother."²

Susan's life reflects this phenomenon. Outwardly or ideologically, she has the family that appears ideal but it does not offer her a space of fulfillment but quiet oppression. So, Lessing criticizes the myth that family naturally satisfies women. The family is exposed as a socially constructed illusion. Though the Rawlings' marriage begins with rational equality, still it subtly emphasizes patriarchal norms. Susan has everything that she had wished. It is she who chooses to marry and have a family. She marries a man she loves. It is she who decides to leave her job after being pregnant. Work is not her passion. No doubt she, as Matthew, has greater freedom. Matthew is engaged in extramarital affairs. When Susan learns this, her dissatisfaction grows and she starts to understand the restriction imposed on her. Her economic dependence reinforces her subordination and restricts her ability to get out of what she not satisfied with. Susan suffers from psychological conflict. For the sake of her family, she represses her independence which leads to her frustration with domestic life. She becomes

restless and anxious. She begins to feel a growing sense of emptiness and loss of identity. Her role as a wife and mother becomes overwhelming, and she feels trapped in domestic routine. She is supposedly free but socially constrained. Moreover, her husband has affairs with other women. She convinces herself about that. She accepts it outwardly with calm “reason,” but internally, her emotional isolation deepens:

It was banal, too, when one night Matthew came home late and confessed he had been to a party, taken a girl home and slept with her. Susan forgave him, of course. Except that forgiveness is hardly the word. Understanding, yes. But if you understand something, you don't forgive it, you are the thing itself: forgiveness is for what you don't understand. Nor had he confessed-what sort of word is that?¹

Susan is no more interested in her children, her house, and her husband. She estranges herself and craves for alienation from everything around her. From the core of her home, she escapes to a room in an attic, then to a small and quiet hotel in Victoria, after that to Wales, and at last she seeks refuge in room nineteen of Fred's Hotel. She rents the room and stays there completely alone to escape her responsibilities. The room offers her a kind of relief from the pressures of her life. In the course of time, her necessity for isolation becomes stronger, and she grows more detached from her family and real life around her. Room Nineteen is a symbol of autonomy. It represents freedom from social roles, a space for self-reflection and psychological escape. Susan experiences a rare sense of peace in this room. Here, she is not controlled by the domestic roles assigned to her but exists just as an individual. Susan, in the end, cannot settle her inner commotion with the expectations of her life. She takes an awful decision and ends her life in Room Nineteen:

She lay on her back on the green satin cover, but her legs were chilly. She got up, found a blanket folded in the bottom of the chest of drawers, and carefully covered her legs with it. She was quite content lying there, listening to the faint soft hiss of the gas that poured into the room, into her lungs, into her brain, as she drifted off into the dark river. ¹

Conclusions:

This is how an educated and intelligent woman ends her life. She commits suicide as she does not feel like fulfilling the roles expected of her. She wants to be a woman in a different way that what society has prepared for her. In fact, the plight of Susan begins when she takes the decision to family which becomes bait that lures her. She takes family as utopia. However, she drifts into the net of family giving birth to four children and leaving her job. And here begins the conflict between societal expectations and individual identity. In fact, the modern domestic life psychologically oppresses the educated and intelligent women like Susan Rawlings undergoes a complete mental breakdown driven by the suffocating pressures of idealized family institution. This leads to intense alienation, loss of identity, and ultimately suicide. In spite of being rational and organized, Susan feels trapped by the roles of wife and mother, experiencing a profound, silent, and desperate need for true solitude.

To conclude, ‘To Room Nineteen’ criticizes the modern family and its effect of women. The story effectively shows the psychological, social, and existential dimensions of female oppression resulting into plight which is outcome of systematic issues within patriarchal societies.

Suggestions:

Susan is denied autonomy, identity, and freedom. This denial slowly poisons her psyche and leads to her tragic end. The story gives a message to re-evaluate patriarchal norms of society and allow space for women to live genuinely.

References:

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